

FINE ART TERMS

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Rakhimov Khusanboy Ne'matjon ogly

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, 3rd year student at the Faculty of Folk Crafts and Applied Arts

Scientific adviser: Umrzaqov Behzod Buronovich

Annotation: *The article is devoted to the etymological analysis at the lessons of fine arts, a brief dictionary of terms of fine arts.*

Key words: *fine arts, terminology, pedagogy, education, lesson, teacher.*

In the visual arts, as in other sciences, there are special terms. But the perfect glossary of fine art terms has yet to be created. This, of course, presents certain difficulties for teachers of universities and professional colleges in teaching students the secrets of the fine arts. In fact, the demand for annotated dictionaries is growing exponentially. swimmers encounter many concepts and terms in the process of learning the secrets of the fine arts. It is a little difficult to find the literal meaning of such terms in the literature.

Nowadays, in textbooks, manuals, brochures and scientific articles, we see that expressions related to fine arts are written in different forms and used in different meanings. To overcome these difficulties, some scientific research has been carried out.

We try to learn the terms and concepts of fine art from literature translated from Russian, as well as from various methodological magazines and newspapers. An analysis of methodological guidelines, manuals and terms used in the literature of recent years shows that there is a difference in the use of fine art terms in the Uzbek language. This leads to a misunderstanding of the meaning of the term and negatively affects the quality of the educational process.

In everyday practice, instead of the word fine art, the term "painting" is often used. However, the Terminology Committee recommended that the word "image" be used instead of the term "image". At the same time, the terms "reproduction", "illustration", "graphics", "painting" are also called "painting or painting". One reason for the differences in terms is ignorance of the true meaning of the terms.

One type of fine art is called "drawing from nature." The term translates as "drawing oneself." The term is used in various translations in books. In our opinion, it would be more correct to take the phrase "drawing on the object itself" as a basis.

Similarly, the word "decorative" is translated as "decorative", "decorative", the term "arts and crafts" in the Uzbek language is used correctly and appropriately.

The use of the terms "image" and "image" in the Uzbek language does not pay much attention to the content. For example, the image of Navoi "Image of Navoi" and so on. "Image" means the appearance on the surface of the eye. The term "image" refers to the artistic depiction of a particular person. In conclusion, the terminology of fine arts in the Uzbek language needs serious development.

General terms are words that have a specific meaning.

The Uzbek language is very rich. A word can have multiple meanings. But not all of these values are the same. Therefore, it is necessary to draw a conclusion and choose the content that is accurate and up-to-date.

For example, the correct placement of a group of objects in front of the eyes is called a "layout". But when we use the term in class, swimmers don't always get along. Therefore, it makes sense to take this concept for "accommodation". A similar phrase "construction" is often used in practice. This term refers to the concept of drawing, which describes the appearance of an object on the surface of the eye. Therefore, the word "construction" is appropriate.

In Uzbek literature, some expressions are used in both languages at the same time. First the name in Uzbek, then the name in Russian in brackets, or vice versa. For example, painting (painting) or painting (painting), architecture (architecture) or architecture (architecture) and others.

Graphics is an international term derived from the Greek "grafo" - to write, draw, and "watercolor" is an international term derived from the Latin "agua" (water), which means "paint". The word "composition" also comes from Latin, and "compositio" means to place, compare and combine in a certain order. In Arabic it means content. The terms "still life", "perspective", "proportion", "portrait" also come from Latin and French and are international terms.

Therefore, not every term can be translated.

There are also terms translated into Uzbek. For example, the words drawing and painting are used in translation with such synonymous words as kalamtasvir and rangtasvir. The term "aerial perspective" is translated as "aerial perspective".

The course uses some terms in Russian and Uzbek. For example: horizon line or horizon line, the word horizon line is used in drawing geometry lessons, the term "horizon line" is used in fine art lessons. Teachers directly use various visual art terms to analyze classroom work. Some teachers call such terms in Russian as "foreground", "middle ground", "far ground", first plan, second plan, third plan. These words do not shed much light on the meaning. Plan in Uzbek means plan. If it is used as a direct translation, it is called the first plan, the second plan, the third plan. Therefore, when analyzing works of fine art, it is advisable to translate the terms in accordance with the content so that they are understandable to swimmers. Experienced art educators use terms such as "front view", "middle view", "far (far) view", or "rear view".

The terms "landscape" and "landscape" are close to each other, but both are ambiguous. While a view of nature is a real reality that we perceive through our ability to see and perceive, a landscape is an artistic representation of that view.

In the process of teaching fine arts, students face some difficulties.

They are due to the following reasons:

- national schools are not fully provided with visual arts textbooks;
- at present, schoolchildren do not have a deep understanding of the meaning of terms in the classroom;
- very few guidelines and recommendations for teaching fine arts;
- terms are inefficiently used in the educational process of pedagogical schools, universities;
- Each of the teachers of institutes and educational institutions that train artists and teachers creates their own conditions. This leads to chaos and uncertainty.

The variety of fine art terms translated into Uzbek can be explained by the following reasons:

1. The absence of a qualified translator leads to a distortion of the form and content of terms.
- 2 In the terminology of modern fine arts in the Uzbek language, several nouns are used in relation to one concept.
3. The reason for the difference in terms is the lack of an explanatory dictionary of fine arts in the Uzbek language.

To regulate and interpret the terminology of fine arts in the Uzbek language, it is necessary to use the following from the general processes of terminology with the features of the Uzbek language:

1. It is necessary to translate international terms translated into Russian without translation into Uzbek. For example, watercolor, asymmetry, stained glass, gallery, harmony, engraving, mosaic, etching, panel, pastel, symmetry, statue, texture, background, stamp, exterior, study and much more.
2. Sometimes, if a suitable term cannot be found in Russian, it is advisable to leave the term in its original form without translation. For example, sighting, palette, sketch, shade, stroke, sitter, achromatic, appliqué, genre, illustration, canvas and others.
3. It is necessary to fully use the internal potential of the Uzbek language in the development of fine art terms in the Uzbek language. Sometimes it is difficult to convey the meaning of a phrase in Russian with a word in Uzbek. Therefore, it is necessary to write two words separated by a dash (-).

For example, contrast - contrast, chiaroscuro - light-shadow, shine - glitter-doK, bust - body-sculpture and so on.

4. When translating terms from Russian into Uzbek, it is necessary to preserve the internal form as much as possible. For example, the term "ornament" in Russian simply means "flower". In Uzbek, this meaning is used in the phrase "pattern". TugriroKi The

term "ornament" should be translated as "house pattern" or "home flower". The term "painting" means "alive, alive" and "writing". It can be seen from the analysis that there is a gap between live writing and color descriptive phrases. The term "painting" is used to translate the content of two similar forms.

5. Along with the terms, it is necessary to translate the names of works of fine art not directly, but according to their content. For example, a relief is a curved face, a bas-relief is a low bend, a high relief is a high bend. The rules outlined above have been used to interpret fine art terms.

When compiling an explanatory dictionary of fine art terms, translating terms, the rules of term formation are based on a number of linguistic analyses. The importance of teaching the concepts of art in integrating the visual literacy of swimmers is great. To teach swimmers the expressions of visual arts, we divide the terms into several groups according to their specific features.

Writing conditions: watercolor, grizzly, achromatic, glare, (light), harmony, contrast, copy, reflex, panel, palette, landscape, chiaroscuro, color, tempera, texture, color, background, fresco, light, sketch, ranglavkha (sketch), canvas, monumental, rangtasvir, mosaic, stained glass.

Graphic terms: autoengraving, book graphics, title, frontispiece, flyleaf, barcode, outline, caricature, woodcut, linocut, sgraffito, print, drawing, poster, silhouette, stamp, emblem, bookplate.

Terms related to sculpture: high bend, bend, low bend, pottery, monumental sculpture, obelisk, bust, monument, profile, symmetry, sculpture, sculpture, statue, sphinx.

Terms related to arts and crafts: asymmetry, poster, glazing, tapestry, arts and crafts, decorator, artist, stage design, pattern, pottery, carving, symbol (sign), texture, sketch, exterior, interior, banner, stencil, symmetry, ceramics, tiles, embroidery.

Terms of composition: harmony, contrast, contour, copy, sketch, size, format, proportion, symbol, symmetry, placement, rhythm, perspective, line, dot, dot, horizon, front view, middle view, distance view, building center, dynamics. composition, stylistic composition...

Terms related to the history of art: ancient art, art of the ancient world, arcade, vandalism, Renaissance art, Russian art, Uzbek fine art, arts and crafts, fine art, capital, classic, statue, sphinx, fresco, contrasting colors.

Terms related to chiaroscuro and colors: coloration, brightness, shadow, hue, gloss, doK, personal shadow, drop shadow, penumbra, hue, color ratio, contrast (contrast), coloristics ...

Terms relating to media: stencil, watercolour, mukalam, sikma paint, watercolour, watercolour, canvas, poster pen, dream, gouache, pastel, felt-tip pen, format, drawing paper, stack, putty, sketch, palette, etc.

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